

A New Ecosystem of Early Music Studies

COST Action CA21161 – A new ecosystem of early music studies (EarlyMuse)

Gender Equality Plan (GEP)

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INTRODUCTION

Besides being a fundamental human right, gender equality is essential to achieve a peaceful and prosperous society, realizing full human potential and sustainable development. It drives economic growth, strengthens democracy, enhances social cohesion, and increases the well-being of all members of society. Despite progress in recent decades, gender inequalities persist in most spheres of social and economic life. Intersectional gender gaps persist in almost all cultural and creative sectors, with cultural professionals experiencing discrimination based on their gender identities. Female artists and cultural workers across the EU typically have less access to creation and production resources, are paid much less than men and are underrepresented in leadership and other decision-making positions, as well as on the market. This is why examples of good practice are even more required and relevant. Their inclusivity and diversity bring forward new ideas and innovative approaches, which better serve a demanding and dynamic society.

In this case, it is the musicological community of EarlyMuse COST Action (<https://earlymuse.eu/>), a Europe-wide scientific network (21/09/2022 – 20/09/2026) that aims to strengthen the place of early music research in Europe. The Action transforms the way that the discipline is studied, redraws the place of early music in higher education, attracts original talent, deploys tools useful to emerging creative industries, and defines public policy in the field of culture. Building on these existing strengths, EarlyMuse brings together scholars from all over Europe to create new opportunities to study this significant part of European cultural heritage.

THE STRUCTURE: CORE GROUP, MANAGEMENT COMMITTEE, WORKING GROUPS AND MEMBERSHIP

Gender balance is very well ensured both in the Core Group (Leadership) and the Management Committee. There are five working groups within the Action: WG 1

Education, WG 2 Sources, WG 3 Publications, WG 4 Performances, WG 5 Policies. Even 4 out of 5 WG leaders are female.

Core Group: 15 members (October 2024)

male 7 (47%)

female 8 (53%)

Management Committee: 49 members (October 2024)

male 27 (55%)

female 22 (45%)

THE MEMBERSHIP OF WGS

As far as the WG membership is concerned, the situation is even more favourable and reaches a perfect gender balance of 50%.

Total number of WGs members: 262 (October 2024)

male 132 (50%)

female 130 (50%)

Gender by WGs (October 2024; each member may join more than one WG)

WG	Male	Female	Total
WG 1 Education	62	48	110
WG 2 Sources	81	63	144
WG 3 Publications	63	55	118
WG 4 Performances	57	48	105
WG 5 Policies	20	33	53

YOUNG MEMBERS

There are 81 young members in the Action (October 2024), which makes 30% of the total number. Within that number, there are 37 male members (46%) and 44 female members (54%). Considering the Action as a whole, 14% of members are young male, while 17% are young female.

ITC MEMBERS

There are 100 WG members with affiliations in Inclusiveness Target Countries. ITC members thus represent 38% of the total WG membership. Of these, 53% are female and 47% are male.

One-third (33) of the members from ITCs are young researchers. The share of young female members from the ITCs compared with total number of Action members is 7% (October 2024).

CURRENT STATE AND PLANS FOR THE FUTURE

When it comes to the gender equality, EarlyMuse is an excellent example and could serve as a role model for other COST Actions, where these results are yet to be achieved (for example in the STEM area). Gender balance within EarlyMuse is achieved at all levels, from the decision-makers to the Action’s members. There is no need to identify and invite participants from the under-represented sex. Gender equality is not only planned or promoted, but already integrated in the very core of the Action. Based on the COST idea of open networking, equal opportunities are accessible for both male and female members, confirming gender equality competencies. This includes various aspects of networking, research, education, and dissemination. Scholars from all over Europe, from diverse backgrounds, who might have historically been under-represented in the cultural and creative industries or come from the Inclusiveness Target Countries, are enabled to meaningfully participate in the Action, which is necessary for its well-functioning and leads to more effective dissemination. As a result, another important aspect is being integrated – the COST Excellence and Inclusiveness Policy, which strongly encourages gender balance of research networks,

as well as the take up of leadership positions by (young) women COST Action participants (<https://www.cost.eu/about/strategy/gender-equality/>, <https://www.cost.eu/about/strategy/excellence-and-inclusiveness/>).

The favourable numbers discussed above are not an end unto themselves. They are only a ground basis for mutual understanding, open dialogue, and the continued fostering of an inclusive environment for all the members. They also raise some questions for us to continue to ponder. For example, WG 5 (Policies) is the smallest by number, but the only WG where females are in the majority. Why is this group more popular with women than men? Could this be an ideal example of how the world would look if it were run by women? Are women's contributions equally valued and highlighted? How to create a new dynamic that would allow more women to occupy positions of responsibility? Conversely, WG 2 (Sources) seems to have a comparably large proportion of male members. Are there professional reasons for that? Or other reasons? We also note that the overall proportion of young female members stands at 17%. As mentioned previously, this may have to do with how "young" is currently defined by COST (under 40 years of age): in our field, entry to the profession often occurs at a later life stage. But it could also be that we can do more to encourage the participation of young researchers and confront the question of their careers.

EarlyMuse will keep on nourishing gender equality and excellence in the upcoming period. Both male and female members, young(er) and old(er), will be encouraged to actively take part in further activities such as meetings, workshops, conferences, and short-term scientific missions. Their collaborative working solves challenges, reaches period goals, and delivers joint results. This is how EarlyMuse COST Action ensures the reputation and inclusivity of musicology as a discipline in the present, and strongly contributes to its perspectives, sustainability, and development in the future.

* Vilena Vrbančić was nominated the gender equality adviser for CA21161 EarlyMuse in August 2024. To learn more about the topic, she took part at the COST Academy Workshop on gender equality in research and innovation, held at the Joint Research Centre in Brussels in October 2024.